

RLocator: Appendix

A.1 Performance comparison of RLocator with prior approaches

Table 1: Performance of RLocator in comparison to prior approaches.

Project	Model	Top 1	Top 5	Top 10	MAP	MRR
AspectJ	RLocator	0.40	0.63	0.70	0.46	0.50
	Cheng et al. [1]	0.46	0.76	0.84	0.38	0.60
	bjXnet [2]	-	-	-	-	-
	DeepLoc [3]	0.45	0.71	0.80	0.42	0.51
	CAST [4]	0.50	0.76	0.83	0.42	0.54
	KGBugLocator [5]	0.50	0.77	0.83	0.42	0.55
Birt	RLocator	0.25	0.41	0.48	0.38	0.41
	Cheng et al.	-	-	-	-	-
	bjXnet	-	-	-	-	-
	DeepLoc	-	-	-	-	-
	CAST	-	-	-	-	-
	KGBugLocator	-	-	-	-	-
Eclipse Platform UI	RLocator	0.37	0.63	0.73	0.42	0.50
	Cheng et al.	-	-	-	-	-
	bjXnet	0.60	0.83	0.90	0.70	0.61
	DeepLoc	0.45	0.70	0.79	0.43	0.53
	CAST	-	-	-	-	-
	KGBugLocator	-	-	-	-	-

JDT	RLocator	0.33	0.61	0.75	0.44	0.45
	Cheng et al.	0.48	0.67	0.81	0.49	0.58
	bjXnet	0.43	0.80	0.88	0.60	0.52
	DeepLoc	0.43	0.65	0.77	0.44	0.53
	CAST	0.43	0.68	0.75	0.38	0.46
	KGBugLocator	0.43	0.69	0.75	0.40	0.47
SWT	RLocator	0.30	0.51	0.58	0.42	0.44
	Cheng et al.	0.60	0.82	0.89	0.62	0.70
	bjXnet	0.52	0.79	0.88	0.65	0.55
	DeepLoc	0.39	0.66	0.77	0.40	0.49
	CAST	0.37	0.70	0.82	0.42	0.50
	KGBugLocator	0.38	0.71	0.83	0.43	0.51
Tomcat	RLocator	0.39	0.55	0.68	0.47	0.51
	Cheng et al.	-	-	-	-	-
	bjXnet	-	-	-	-	-
	DeepLoc	0.54	0.72	0.81	0.56	0.62
	CAST	0.50	0.76	0.82	0.55	0.61
	KGBugLocator	0.51	0.75	0.82	0.56	0.62

A.2 Example of nested exception

```

public class NestedException{
    public static void main(String[] args) {
        String [] input = {"adwd", "d3d3", null};
        for (String item: input) {
            System.out.println(getLength(item));
        }
    }
    public static int getLength(String text) {
        return strip(text).length();
    }
    public static String strip(String text) {
        return text.strip();
    }
}

```

```

Exception in thread "main" java.lang.NullPointerException:
Cannot invoke "String.strip()" because
"<parameter1>" is null
at NestedException.strip(NestedException.java:15)
at NestedException.getLength(NestedException.java:11)
at NestedException.main(NestedException.java:7)

```

Figure 1: Example code creating nested exception

Table 2: Median bug report quality of the projects.

Project	Median bug report quality	Std. of bug report quality
AspectJ	1.04	0.15
Birt	0.87	0.26
Eclipse Platform UI	0.75	0.38
JDT	0.83	0.18
SWT	0.79	0.32
Tomcat	0.81	0.3

In Figure 1, we illustrate an example of a nested exception. In this example, two exceptions are encountered, originating from the "getLength" and "strip" methods. Nevertheless, a developer can identify that the fundamental cause of the exception is rooted in the "strip" method.

A.3 Analysis regarding bug quality

In terms of Mean Average Precision (MAP), RLocator achieved the highest performance among the five tools in three out of six projects (AspectJ, Birt, and JDT). The performance in the Tomcat project was equal. However, RLocator did not achieve the highest performance in the Eclipse Platform UI and SWT projects.

The underperformance of RLocator in Eclipse Platform UI and SWT can be attributed to several factors. Upon close inspection of the analyzed data, we find that the quality of bug reports can significantly impact the performance of bug localization tools. Following the approach of IMaChecker [6], we calculate the median bug report quality for all projects. A bug report can achieve the highest quality (=4) if it includes reproduction steps, fix suggestions, code snippets, and user content. Table 2 displays the median bug report quality for the projects.

As shown in Table 2, AspectJ bug reports have the highest quality. Conversely, Eclipse Platform UI, SWT, and Tomcat have the lowest-quality bug reports. The standard deviation of bug report quality indicates that Eclipse Platform UI, SWT, and Tomcat have the most fluctuation. The low quality and inconsistency of these bug reports create a substantial lexical gap between the natural language used in bug reports and the programming language in source files [7, 8]. This gap may have the impact of reducing the effectiveness of RLocator’s text-based search mechanism. Future studies could focus on integrating techniques like query reformulation to improve RLocator’s performance by enhancing bug report quality.

Another possible reason for RLocator’s underperformance is the similarity between bug reports and source code files. We define similarity as:

$$similarity = \frac{(Bug\ Report\ Tokens \cap File\ Tokens)}{Number\ of\ Unique\ Tokens\ in\ Bug\ Report} \quad (1)$$

Table 3: The median similarity score of the projects.

Project	Similarity Score	Std. of bug report quality
AspectJ	0.58	0.15
Birt	0.29	0.26
Eclipse Platform UI	0.30	0.38
JDT	0.43	0.18
SWT	0.33	0.32
Tomcat	0.39	0.3

Table 3 shows that Birt, Eclipse Platform UI, and SWT have the lowest similarity scores. The similarity metric measures the helpful information in the bug reports that assist the model in relating source code files with bug reports. A low similarity score makes it challenging for the model to capture relevant information accurately [2]. Training the model on a larger dataset could help the bug localization model learn enough vocabulary to draw connections, even if the similarity score is low [9].

References

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